

- It is recommended to place 1 to 3 double-cladodes cuttings per hole, depending on the growing system and the shaping pruning.
- Avoid planting during rainy periods.

2.1. IRRIGATION

- Prickly pear is drought-tolerant and can be grown under rainfed conditions.
- However, under arid or semi-arid climates, in intensive systems or in orchards managed with the "Scozzolatura" technique irrigation becomes necessary to ensure good productivity.

The "Scozzolatura" (this technique involves removing all flower buds and young cladodes during the full flowering stage to stimulate the appearance of another wave of flowering and young cladodes).

- After plantation, avoid overwatering and direct water contact with the cladodes to prevent rot. Moderate regular watering (6–15 L per plant per week, depending on plant age and soil type) during summer is advised in early years.
- For intensive orchards, after "Scozzolatura", supply 700–1200 m³/ha of water, depending on planting density, climate condition and soil type during fruit growth to enhance cladode fertility, fruit quality, and prepare next season's yield.

2. ORCHARDS ESTABLISHMENT

- Before establishing a new prickly pear orchard, the selected variety must be suited to market demands, local edapho-climatic conditions and resistant to the cochineal insect.
- Planting material (cladodes) must be free from abnormalities, such as minerals deficiency symptoms or signs of pest attacks. Cuttings should be taken from productive prickly pear plants to facilitate the verification of genetic authenticity.
- Use double-cladode cuttings from mature plants to enable earlier fruiting. After cutting, cladodes should be stored in a dry and ventilated area until the "cut end" is fully healed.
- The soil preparation is highly recommended to loosen the topsoil to a depth of about 50 cm. Then, individual planting holes (40 x 40 x 40 cm) or furrows (30 cm wide and depth) can be dug along the rows using tillage equipment.
- For fertilization, apply 5–7 kg of compost, 100–200 g of phosphorus, and 100–150 g of potassium per planting hole. These are indicative doses and should be adjusted based on soil characteristics, fertilizer type, and cultivation method.
- Plant spacing depends on the production system (extensive to intensive): 4 m x 6 m, 5 m x 5 m, 4 m x 5 m, 3 m x 5 m, 2 m x 5 m, etc. Rows should ideally be oriented north-south to maximize light exposure and plant growth.

TECHNICAL GUIDE ON THE GOOD PRACTICES FOR THE CULTIVATION OF SPINELESS PRICKLY PEAR

Opuntia ficus-indica (L.) Mill., known as prickly pear, is a species native to Mexico and it has been progressively domesticated. It was introduced to Tunisia in the 17th century by the Moors expelled from Andalusia. Today, the plant covers several hundred thousand hectares across the country. Its adaptability to arid climatic conditions has contributed to its expansion. It naturally produces edible fruits during the summer in the Mediterranean region. The prickly pear is mainly cultivated for its fruits, highly appreciated by consumers, for its seeds, from which oil is extracted for cosmetic use but also for the cladodes as livestock feed.

Opuntia ficus indica at the moment of flowering

1. OPTIMAL CULTIVATION CONDITIONS

- Avoid areas prone to frost, where winter temperatures can drop to -10 °C or below. However, the prickly pear cactus tolerates high temperatures, exceeding 40 °C.
- Avoid hydromorphic soils or those causing root asphyxiation. It prefers light-textured, well-structured soils with good drainage, and a pH ranging from slightly acidic to slightly alkaline.

The Scozzolatura technique

Planting double cladodes

FRUITING PRUNING

The prickly pear cactus primarily produces its fruits on the cladodes of the previous year. The purpose of fruiting pruning is to renew these productive organs, optimize light penetration into the canopy, and facilitate access for phytosanitary treatments. Cladodes growing inside the canopy, which are generally less fertile, create favorable areas for the establishment of bioaggressors and should be removed.

2.4. PLANT PROTECTION

- Aside from the cochineal insect (*Dactylopius opuntiae*), prickly pear is one of the most resilient plant species and generally faces no major phytosanitary problems.
- Cochineal management relies primarily on resistant varieties. Complementary cultural practices help reduce pest pressure.
- Regular maintenance pruning improves air flow, light penetration and increases the treatments' efficiency.
- Biological control using natural predators and fostering their establishment in the orchard is a key tool in managing cochineal infestations.

Mycorrhizal biofertilisation in new plantations

- Intercropping with feed or food legumes between prickly pear rows is an organic fertilization technique. These legumes fix atmospheric nitrogen (N₂), enriching soil nitrogen levels and improving plant nutrition.
- The sowing rate of legumes depends on the species. For example: Vetch: 60 kg/ha and Fenugreek: 70 kg/ha .

Intercropping with legumes (Vetch)

2.3. PRUNING

SHAPING PRUNING

Depends on the growing system (Vase shape, narrow hedge, bush, etc.). In the first year, the pruning aims to encourage vertical growth.

For vase shape it is recommended to plant three cladodes per hole to ensure balanced structural branches.

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2.2. FERTILIZATION

2.2.1. CHEMICAL FERTILIZATION

The nutritional needs of prickly pear vary depending on management practices, soil properties, and the plant's phenological stage.

- Annual nutrient requirements per hectare typically range from: Nitrogen (N): 150–270 kg , Phosphorus (P): 100–180 kg and Potassium (K): 120–200 kg.

Fertilizer applications should be fractioned throughout the year according to plant development stages:

- At the beginning of the season (spring): prioritize phosphorus (P) and nitrogen (N) to stimulate root development and vegetative/floral structure formation.
- During bud growth: nitrogen (N) needs exceed phosphorus (P) and potassium (K).
- During fruit development and ripening: increase potassium (K) supply to support fruit formation and improve fruit quality.

2.2.2. ORGANIC FERTILIZATION

It's a mandatory technique in organic systems and strongly recommended in conventional orchards to reduce chemical inputs.

Organic fertilization using beneficial microorganisms (mycorrhizal and bacterial biofertilizers) improves production sustainability. Mycorrhizal biofertilizers are applied while planting the cladodes or after plantation for old orchards. In this case, it is applied by digging two 25 cm deep holes about 50 cm from the trunk on opposite sides .

Mycorrhizal biofertilisation at plantation

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